

POLYETHYLENE FIBERS - POLYETHYLENE MATRIX COMPOSITES: PREPARATION AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

By utilizing the difference in melting points of UHMPE fiber (147°C) and HDPE matrix (133°C), single polymer composites were fabricated under various processing conditions. Because of the chemical similarity of the composite components, good bonding at the fiber-matrix interface could be expected. The TMA of the fiber showed three regimes of contraction according to the values of the thermal expansion coefficient. DSC analyses of either the fiber or the composite specimens did not show any appreciable changes after various thermal treatments. The tensile strength and modulus values of the composite appeared to be fairly high and close to those reported for other composites reinforced with PE fibers.

Key words: single polymer composite, Spectra fiber, high density polyethylene matrix, thermal properties, tensile testing.

INTRODUCTION

Polyethylene (PE) fibers produced by gel-spinning from ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene have a highly oriented crystalline structure that results in high mechanical performance. For example, Spectra 1000 PE fibers, by Allied Sigma, are characterized by their tensile strength and modulus values of 2.9 GPa and 172 GPa, respectively¹. However, their chemical composition and physical morphology renders ultrahigh modulus polyethylene (UHMPE) fibers inert and incapable of forming strong interfacial bonding with polymeric matrices. This is regarded as a major disadvantage, because the mechanical properties of composite materials are greatly affected by the degree of adhesion at the fiber - matrix interface.

A literature survey reveals only a small number of papers that analyze UHMPE fiber - high density polyethylene (HDPE) matrix composites, which are the subject of the present study. Those papers are devoted mostly to the investigation of transcrystalline growth of HDPE on the fiber surface^{2,3} and to the preparation^{2,4} and mechanical performance of composite materials⁴.

This study has been undertaken to investigate the effect of various processing conditions on the mechanical behavior of the composite. In addition, the question of appropriate bonding at the fiber - matrix interface has to be solved. A potential key to solving this problem is the chemical similarity of the fiber and the matrix. The different physical states of the composite constituents lead to an appreciable difference in their melting points (the melting temperatures are about 130°C and 150°C for the matrix and the fiber, respectively), that gives a sufficiently wide manufacture temperature "window". This "window", coupled with a sheath - core

structure of the fiber, may allow surface melting of the fiber, without affecting the highly ordered core, thus retaining its good mechanical performance and improving bonding at the fiber - matrix interface⁵.

COMPOSITE FABRICATION

50 μm thick films of HDPE of generic source were used as the matrix and UHMPE fibers, Spectra 1000 (Allied Sigma) as the reinforcement.

Unidirectional composite laminae were prepared in two stages. At first the as received (AR) fiber tow was wound by a manual filament winding machine on a flat mandrel covered by HDPE sheets. The mandrel was then removed from the winding machine, placed between additional HDPE sheets and pressed under 0.32 or 0.48 MPa at 133, 135, 144 and 150°C for 60, 50, 40 and 30 min, respectively. After that it was either slowly cooled (SC) under pressure by switching the press off, or water quenched (WQ) by dipping in water at the ambient temperature. In all of the experiments the fiber volume fraction was within the range of 45-55%.

Full experimental details of the matrix, the fiber and unidirectional composite laminae investigations using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermomechanical analyses (TMA), tensile testing and the hot stage crystallization unit attached to a polarizing microscope are given elsewhere⁵.

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

As seen from Figure 1, the coefficients of thermal expansion are found to be negative over the whole temperature range of the experiment. Such a behavior of PE fibers is due to the presence of a considerable amount of macromolecular chains, that are highly oriented along the

Figure 1. Expansion coefficients of the Spectra 1000 fibers parallel to orientation.

fiber axis, forming so-called continuous crystals⁶. This supermolecular structure, together with the negative thermal expansion in the c-axis (chain direction) of PE crystals, lead to contraction in the direction parallel to orientation.

Three temperature regimes of fiber contraction were detected. The data of Figure 1 indicate that the first interval from 30 to 90°C is characterized by a constant value of expansion coefficient of $-4.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. In the second regime from 90 to 134°C the contraction increases continually (the coefficient of thermal expansion decreases to $-1.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) with irreversible dimensional changes. The reason for this behavior lays probably with increasing the mobility and contraction of extended polymer chains at higher temperatures as a result of relaxation processes (of previously stressed tie chains, for example). Such processes lead to a structural reorganization of the fiber (annealing effects), starting from its skin. At higher temperatures a

sharp drop of the curve occurs, indicating a strong premelting contraction (almost 90%) of the fiber (the third regime). This is yet another indication of the perfect chain orientation in the AR fiber.

Figure 2 shows DSC thermograms of the Spectra 1000 fiber, the HDPE film, and of the single polymer PE composite. As seen, the fibers melt at a higher temperature than the matrix which enables the molding of the composites.

Figure 2. DSC plots of (a) Spectra 1000 fiber, (b) HDPE matrix and (c) a typical PE composite (0.48 MPa, 133°C, WQ).

The peak at 132°C in the DSC trace of the composite corresponds to melting of spherulites in the HDPE matrix. In contrast to the previously reported data², no evidence of transcrystallinity at the fiber - matrix interface can be seen. In addition, no indication of fiber annealing during composite manufacture can be observed, as the fiber peak in the composite remains in its original position. The possible explanation of this observation can lay with the procedure of composite preparation, according to which the fibers were stretched on a flat metallic mandrel by filament winding, put between the press platens and compressed. Such conditions (especially the continuous stretching during the winding process) can result in lateral constraint on the fibers, impeding their annealing. Indeed, the DSC analysis of the pure fibers processed in the press under composites manufacture conditions did not show any change in comparison with the AR fiber, whilst annealing of the fibers in the DSC under the same conditions (but without pressure) displayed considerable structure changes.

Consistently with the results discussed above, the DSC traces of the PE composites were found to be insensitive to the type of thermal treatment applied. However, they did reflect differences due to the different crystallinities of the SC and WQ matrices.

Whereas the degree of crystallinity was sensitive to the thermal cycle, no significant transcrystallinity could be developed under a variety of experimental conditions. These included different potent fiber surface treatments recommended in the literature, such as oxygen plasma,

chromic acid etching and solvent (toluene) washing. In addition, washing of the matrix by xylene and 1,2-dichlorobenzene was employed, to remove impurities and thereby decrease the nucleation density in the bulk, to make the fiber surface more effective as a heterogeneous nucleator. It was thought that the inability to develop a significant transcrystalline layer laid with the type of the HDPE matrix. When that material was replaced by another HDPE (Petrothene, from USI) transcrystallinity could be grown readily.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The values of the tensile strength (see Figure 3) and modulus obtained here are comparable to those of PE composite laminates fabricated with another type of UHMPE fibers (Dyneema SK 60) and HDPE matrix (tensile strength of 1.1 GPa, tensile modulus of 73 GPa at fiber volume fraction of 75%)⁴. They are also comparable to those of Spectra 900 - epoxy resin composite (tensile strength of 1.1 GPa, tensile modulus of 26 GPa, fiber volume fraction of 61%)¹.

Figure 3. Effect of processing conditions on tensile strength of PE composite measured in the longitudinal direction (standard deviation bars are given for WQ material fabricated under a pressure of 0.48 MPa).

Although the results in Figure 3 do not exhibit significant trends with either temperature, pressure or thermal history, two observations could still be made. The first is the absence of a clear property decrease at the higher processing temperature regime, where fiber relaxation starts, and the second is the apparent maximum for a processing temperature of 135°C. The first observation results probably from a relaxation prevention condition that is imposed on the fiber during the manufacture stage. A possible reason for this condition is the molding pressure that induces lateral constraint on the fiber. Another possible reason for relaxation prevention is the stretching of the wound fibers on the mandrel, which prevents their shrinkage during the molding.

The maximum at 135°C for the strength and modulus could result from the effect of two simultaneous, competing processes⁷. One is the annealing process which is expected to produce relaxation and property decrease, and the other is the induction at higher temperature of transcrystallization or co-crystallization at the interface, resulting probably in increased fiber - matrix adhesion.

CONCLUSIONS

Molding of prepreps prepared by filament winding UHMPE fibers on the HDPE films is a feasible way of producing high performance single polymer PE composites, whose mechanical properties are comparable with those of other composites reinforced with PE fibers. No clear

property decrease was observed at the higher processing temperature regime, where fiber relaxation is enhanced, probably because of the pressure related transverse constraint. The maximum at 135°C for the tensile strength and modulus of the composite could result from the effect of two competing processes. One is the annealing of the fiber leading to a property decrease, and the other is the induction of co-crystallization at the interface, promoting possibly an increase in adhesion. The strength and modulus were found to be invariant with the cooling treatment following composite manufacture.

In contrast to previously published data, no transcrystallinity growth at the fiber - matrix interface was viewed even for chemical and plasma surface treated fibers. However, after replacing the HDPE matrix used by another HDPE pronounced transcrystallinity developed. It is therefore concluded, that the exact type of the PE matrix has a strong influence on its ability to transcrystallize.

It is thought that the stretching of the fibers during composite preparation along with the molding pressure are the main factors that impede fiber annealing. The TMA showed negative thermal expansion of UHMPE fibers over the complete temperature range of the experiment. The fibers exhibited three temperature regimes of contraction according to the values of the thermal expansion coefficient.

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